

Equity Issues in Educational Data Mining from an Epistemological Perspective

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Abstract. Educational Data Mining (EDM) has shown interesting scientific results lately. However, little has been discussed about philosophical questions regarding the type of knowledge produced in this area. Bispo Jr. (2019) presented two epistemological issues that emerged from EDM research. This paper aims to deepen this discussion by presenting the equity issues that originated from this initial work.

Keywords: Equity · STEM Education · Data Mining · Epistemology

1 Introduction

One of the emerging challenges in Science, Technology, Engineering and Math (STEM) education refers to diversity [10, p. 19:2]. Existing differences in a classroom can be a source of wealth and beauty. But they can also be a source of tensions that can generate conflicts. These conflicts are directly associated with the existence of privilege deriving from these differences.

According to Parker and Guzdial [36, p. 1], privilege is “an unearned, unasked-for advantage gained because of the way society views an aspect of a student’s identity, such as race, ethnicity, gender, socioeconomic status, and language”. The Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE⁴) conducted the Continuous National Survey by Domicile Sample (PNAD *Contínua*⁵) in 2018, relating the theme of Information and Communication Technology. This survey revealed that one in four Brazilian people does not have internet access. Suppose we admit that a fraction of these Brazilians who do not have internet access were composed of students in an undergraduate computing program. What would be the impact of this reality on their formation quality? What would be the difference in the formation quality of these students relating to other ones? Scenarios

⁴ IBGE stands for *Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística* in Brazilian Portuguese.

⁵ PNAD *Contínua* stands for *Pesquisa Nacional por Amostra de Domicílios Contínua* in Brazilian Portuguese.

like this show that the differences can convert in privilege to a specific social stratum of the scholar community.

The understanding that there is inequality in the conditions in student context is fundamental for promoting social justice in STEM education. This perception allows the professor/teacher to reorganize their priorities and build a more honest frame of emerging problems deriving from the diversity of their scholar community.

When I use the term equity in this work, I refer to inequality of opportunities in education. Lewis and colleagues [26, p. 482] assert that: “*Equality* refers to the state where everyone has or is allocated the same things in the same degree, whereas *equity* typically refers to having access to what is needed. [...] In general, [...] equity, and not equality, defines fair and just learning opportunities” (my emphasis).

Parallely to strict concerns about equity issues, there are other ways to improve the quality of education, like Educational Data Mining (EDM). EDM is an emergent and interdisciplinary research area that deals with developing methods to explore data from educational contexts [40]. Some results of this area characterize (i) dropout [28,33,15], (ii) motivation [51,43], and (iii) student performance [20,48,17].

EDM uses computational approaches to analyze educational data aiming to study educational issues. However, there is little attention to philosophical questions concerning the knowledge kind produced in this area. This kind of problematization is not properly addressed in systematic reviews published in recent years [14,27,35,37,40,44,49]. There is a mention so briefly in [13] about the epistemology weakness of learning analytics.

However, epistemological issues involving some scientific assertions concerning Big Data, for example, are present in literature [25,7]. In Biological Sciences, it is common to use a large mass of data to conduct empirical research (e.g., NCBI databases⁶). Questions about the kind of generated data from Big Data (and its scientific relevance) have been appointed and discussed in these works.

I addressed epistemological issues in EDM in this Portuguese work [4]. However, I did not appropriately cover emergent equity issues from this perspective in my discussion. Thus, this work aims to present equity issues in EDM from the perspective of two epistemological issues: (i) an issue of ontological nature about the content of obtained knowledge; and (i) another issue of deontological nature about the agenda and the adopted principles by the researcher of STEM education to the detriment of results of their research.

The remaining work is divided as follows. Section 2 describes the main concepts of EDM. Section 3 presents the epistemology and its guiding questions. Section 4 structures equity issues from two epistemological questions in EDM. And, at last, Section 5 delineates the final remarks, and some guidelines are suggested concerning the issues raised in this work.

⁶ NCBI stands for National Center for Biotechnology Information. See more in <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>.

2 Data Mining and Education

One of the main rationales for the arising of data mining (DM) is availability. Digitalization allowed access to vast data that was not available before. Organizations, through their managers and/or employees, have access to this large volume of data at a lower cost [29].

One of the presuppositions of DM is that there is implicit information in this enormous mass of data [18]. A process directly associated with DM is knowledge discovery (KD). The definition of KD is the extraction of implicit information, previously unknown and potentially useful, from data [8]. The information extraction is performed through specific techniques like pattern recognition [34].

DM has applications in more varied spheres of knowledge. We can cite, in the science sphere, analysis of satellite images and organic compounds, recommendation systems in medical diagnoses, and data analysis of the learning process. In the market sphere, we can cite automatic detection of frauds in credit cards, sentiment analysis, forecasting of financial time series (e.g., stock exchanges), and target public identification for a specified sector.

A more specified context is Education. The educational data mining (EDM) area arises probably with the work publication of Anjewierden [2]. This work used DM to identify student profiles. Since then, a range of research projects has been conducted into this cut.

EDM researchers use a variety of data sources to do their research [41, p. xi]. This data are derived from intelligent tutors, educational systems based on computers, online discussion forums, electronic diary classes, and digital academic records of students, among others. This large volume of data has proportioned new ways to study the learning process.

EDM contributes in diverse directions. We can cite as examples (i) visualization of a large volume of data, (ii) statistical analysis from learning management systems (LMS) data, and the production of (iii) classification, (iv) clustering, and (v) rules of association in repositories of educational data [41, p. 3-4].

3 Concepts in Epistemology

Epistemology is the Philosophy branch known as the Theory of Knowledge [39]. It is the study of knowledge and its justified beliefs [47]. Its advent happened in ancient Greece in conjunction with the emergence of Philosophy. [19].

A set of issues makes up part of the interest of epistemology. We can cite some of them like (i) “What are necessary and sufficient conditions of knowledge?”, (ii) “What are its sources?”, (iii) “What is its structure?”, (iv) “What are its limits?” [47]. The question, “What can be known?”, also is a topic of interest in epistemology.

Epistemology provides necessary tooling for a self-criticizing of scientific research. When it asks about the sources of knowledge and its limits, the sciences have the opportunity to revisit themselves and properly structure the knowledge nature produced by them. Epistemology promotes, as part of one of its areas,

what is known as the Philosophy of Science, allowing a refining and evolving process of sciences and of scientific paradigms that emerged (and possibly will emerge) during their history [9].

It is interesting to highlight that STEM has similar questions to Epistemology. We can give as an example the questions listed in several books of Automata Theory, like “What are the fundamental capabilities and limitations of computers?” [46]. However, instead to desire to understand the limits of computability, epistemology aims to know the limits of knowledge.

For EDM, epistemology can provide an important framework to understand the results generated by itself. There are more and more incentives to adopt technologies in educational environments. And, before this, it is necessary to understand when, how, and what are the conditions for including EDM can supply a relevant scientific contribution to this area. All of these questions critically impact equity, diversity, and inclusion issues in STEM education.

We will present and discuss some relations between epistemology and pedagogical worldview (Section 3.1) and between epistemology and deontology (Section 3.2).

3.1 Epistemology and Pedagogical Worldview

Some epistemological issues are developed to establish a pedagogical worldview. It is possible to identify this effort, for instance, in the work of Edgar Morin [31]. About the seven knowledge necessary for future education, Morin approaches questions of epistemological order at least in three of this knowledge.

The first necessary knowledge, pointed out by Morin, is related to the blindness of knowledge. The author asserts that the function of education is “to show that there is no knowledge that not be, at some degree, threatened by the error and illusion”. It makes part of education to teach the limits of own knowledge, pointing their own weak points and their own fragilities.

Another necessary knowledge listed by Morin is the principles of pertinent knowledge. The author asserts that education needs “to situate everything in the context and in the planetary complex”. The complex thinking [30] is one of the elements that guides the education proposal of Morin. It is necessary that the knowledge be integrated and articulated with the whole, avoiding a fragmented education, decontextualized from the world.

Lastly, another necessary knowledge, identified by the author, is to teach comprehension. Morin points out the conditions required for knowledge in a global era, interconnected by networks and media, as the “condition and guaranteeing of intellectual and moral solidarity of humanity”. At this point, it realizes the closer link between epistemological and deontological aspects [32].

3.2 Epistemology and Deontology

According to previously identified, there is a proximity between epistemological and deontological issues. Deontology is one of the kinds of normative theories

concerning choices that are morally required, forbidden, or allowed [1]. Generally, deontology is treated together with the ethic area and is concerned with questions associated with the duty.

The epistemological question “What can I know?” can have a deontological perception under various circumstances. One of these is associated with the limitations related to the duty. For instance, admit that a person can have access to the personal annotation diary of an intimate friend. Access to that information may even exist indeed. However, this person can refuse to read it due to questions involving the respect of their friend, motivated maybe by the existence of a social protocol.

Thus, the access limitations to this information may not be from physical or cognitive nature. They can be limitations of a normative nature. And this norm may be imposed in an intrinsic or extrinsic way on the individual. Hence, external duress (or comprehension) can exist for fulfilling this duty, or internal comprehension (or duress) that that limit should be respected.

At Education, it is usual to see a professor/teacher adopt a particular work pedagogy. This pedagogy guides them in their professional practice through the principles that carry them to see both their workplace and everyone involved. Some choices made in the sphere of their practice are taking in consonance with this “educational worldview” adopted by this professional.

For this work pedagogy, the term “educational paradigm” [16,3] is used. For the authors, an educational paradigm is composed of four elements:

1. an ontology that is a theory of existence;
2. an epistemology that is a theory of knowledge, both of specific knowledge of an individual and of the shared knowledge with all human beings;
3. a methodology to acquiring and validating the knowledge, and
4. a pedagogy that is a theory of teaching that means to facilitate learning according to the epistemology.

In this way, it is natural to hope that the professional exercise of professors/teachers depends directly on the educational paradigm they adopted. Once they adopt this paradigm, their principles and chosen presuppositions will serve as deontological advisors of their practice. Thus, epistemological issues have a closer relation to deontological ones in Education. For instance, admitting that it is necessary to foster an ethical professor/teacher [12,21,6], concerned social justice [50], assuming explicitly their intentionality [5] in STEM education.

4 Epistemological Equity Issues in EDM

I present and discuss to follow two epistemological equity questions in EDM. The first concerns the ontological nature of obtained knowledge content (Section 4.1). And the second concerns the deontological nature relating to agenda and adopted principles by the research in STEM education (Section 4.2).

4.1 Issues of Ontological Nature

An important aspect to highlight in DM is the ontological nature of the generated knowledge. In DM, the knowledge is generated by supplying data to an algorithm. From this data, patterns are obtained through specific techniques of classification.

It is essential to realize the nature of these techniques of pattern classification. All of them are built upon an inductive perspective of knowledge. From that data, patterns are justified and determined. These patterns typically are used for predictive ends in data processing in a future moment.

The emergent issue from this fact is how people use the generated results in EDM. I have at least two sources of problems concerning the nature of this generated knowledge. Both are derivated from a lack of statistical representativeness of data, which I present as follows.

The first problem concerns the spatial dimension of data. The generated patterns reflect features belonging to those extracted data. And not necessarily this data reflect existing features in the population of elements as a whole. It is necessary to know the power that the knowledge of inductive nature can proportionate. And it is also essential to understand the limitations associated with it. It is possible that although exists a large amount of available data to be used in any EDM algorithm, this data can be little representative to provide a minimum basement, supplying a pattern that does not correctly represent the specific context that it desires to observe.

An illustrative scenario would be to use all generated data from LMS for an EDM algorithm. Admit that from this data, it desires to predict a specific behavior of students, observing the generated data through the access made by students of an Information System (IS) program. However, imagine that most of the access was made by other computing students (e.g., from the Software Engineering (SE) program). In this case, the generated pattern will be strongly biased by the number of data points that is superior for SE students than IS ones. It is necessary to have a critical reading of the generated results by the algorithm or a previous selection of data that will be used in the pattern recognition step.

Let's extend this scenario involving an equity issue, changing the two previous groups. Instead of IS and SE programs, we can think of the first group of students with good access to LMS (G1) and the second group, socially marginalized, having critical problems when accessing LMS (G2). It is not difficult to realize that a biased data source can exist due to equity issues of structural nature.

The second problem concerns the temporal dimension of data. Although there is no apparent lack of statistical representativeness, it is possible that the data collection momentum significantly affects the power of prediction of the generated pattern. A pattern generalization can be properly used for forecasting points in temporal series closer to the momentum of extraction of this data. However, the temporal distance between the data collection and the use of EDM generated pattern can distune in a way that this data can naturally lose its predictive capability due to being so far from the current data context.

A possible scenario would be a university with access to a large volume of data from its students since its foundation. To digitalize this data, it wants to build a newcomer student profile in a given course using DM algorithms. Imagine that the collected data time range was of 50 years. Probably, the reasons that led the students to choose a given course varied significantly into this range. Extracting a student profile considering the whole of this data universe, despising its diverse temporal particularities, will fatally lead an educational manager to a wrong understanding of the information they need to obtain.

This is intriguing because several authors have already addressed most of these problems, for instance, in reports of inductive fallacies in Logic [42]. The crucial problem concerning EDM is the implicit presuppositions that many people carry out themselves both in relation to technologies and their fascination with a large amount of data [24]. The simple admission that the immense data quantity allied with any technology naturally makes arise the knowledge that educational managers need is one of the main responsible for conducting some researchers to these misunderstands.

Beyond these issues, there still are other ones of ontological nature. The process of “knowledge discovery” is also misunderstood by researchers in STEM education. There is a specific discussion about the nature of knowledge and its intrinsic relation to human beings (and not machines). For Waldemar Setzer [45], knowledge is intimately linked to the concepts of information and semantics, being an activity possible to be performed exclusively by human beings. In this direction, machines can process data only (and not information). And, as a natural consequence, machines could not do “knowledge discovery” in a strict term.

Still, under this perspective, it is possible to use the expression “knowledge discovery”. It is enough to see EDM through the lens of an information system in a way that technology (EDM) would be a part of its composition [23]. All stakeholders would also be part of this large concept of EDM besides all interrelations among machines, people, and organizations.

4.2 Issues of Deontological Nature

Another essential aspect to highlight in EDM is the deontological nature of the generated knowledge. Usually, professors/teachers, students, managers, and other educational stakeholders use this knowledge as input during the decision-making process. EDM situates itself, in this process, as a provider of differentiated data, being, in some cases, this data more crucial than the others.

In this direction, it is necessary to realize the possible conflicts, in deontological terms, that the “discovered knowledge” by EDM can provoke. The suggested data can antagonize moral principles, duties, and protocols socially accepted in an educational organization. Some suggestions from EDM can collide with cultural values historically built and consolidated by a community.

[11] presented the existing risks of automatic knowledge discovery from data produced by humans in a natural language. In some scenarios, the authors indicate that the algorithms can reproduce prejudices and stereotypes present in our

society. For instance, names of African origin were more associated with negative words than ones of European origin.

Thus, it is necessary to pay attention to the kind of knowledge that is being discovered when we use EDM. EDM algorithms can counter, if used without care, defended values expressed by a scholar community in a pedagogical project, for instance. The obtained patterns usually reflect more faithfully to reality, as it is, than to desired and searched values of a scholar community. Knowing to read and interpret the result of these algorithms is essential to explore all potential that EDM offers to STEM education.

Other aspects concerning transparency and governance of these DM systems have been discussed recently. The need to create an “algorithmic social contract” [38] is arising as an imperative to regulate these systems that involve several values among various societal stakeholders. EDM will also need to cover these issues solidly in this direction, walking together all existing efforts.

5 Final Remarks

This work aimed to present equity issues in EDM from the perspective of two epistemological issues: (i) an issue of ontological nature about the content of obtained knowledge; and (i) another issue of deontological nature about the agenda and the adopted principles by the researcher of STEM education to the detriment of results of their research. Some pitfalls of EDM use were discussed, pointing out the existing risks at each listed dimension.

Before this, it is necessary to reassert EDM’s importance and potential to contribute to the proposition of mediator artifacts in education. The new communication technologies allowed new mediations in the educational scenario as a whole [22, p. 45]. Ignoring its importance is denying all possibilities to build a coherent education environment with the defended values for our society today and for the society that we will want to build for the future.

However, it is necessary to use these technologies, including DM, in a critical way consistent with their strengths and limitations. The critical spirit and moderate skepticism disseminated into the science should be defended as essential for constantly revisiting our research findings and coherently re-elaborating our knowledge, beliefs, and values. The fallacy that technology arises as a species of “Messiah” to solve all existing problems of humanity, including those educational ones, can lead researchers to groundless conclusions. These conclusions can do a disservice to EDM, mainly when we promise a result that is impossible to deliver genuinely.

The essential guideline is to establish a continuous exercise for reconciliation of found discoveries in EDM with all rich discussions already presented by Philosophy of Science about the knowledge nature and its reach. This perennial exercise reinforces the advances reached by this area, guaranteeing the finding credibility before all educational stakeholders.

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